

STANFORD UNIVERSITY PUBLICATIONS
UNIVERSITY SERIES

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VOLUME II

NUMBER 2

Studies on Scurvy

By

ARTHUR W. MEYER

and

LEWIS M. McCORMICK

STANFORD UNIVERSITY PRESS
STANFORD UNIVERSITY, CALIFORNIA

1928

CONTENTS

PART	PAGE
I. THE SYMPTOMATOLOGY AND GROSS MORPHOLOGY OF EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY IN THE GUINEA PIG, by <i>Arthur W. Meyer</i>	7
REFERENCES	40
PLATES I AND II, AND EXPLANATION OF PLATES.....	<i>following</i> 44
II. THE MINUTE MORPHOLOGY OF EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY IN THE GUINEA PIG, by <i>Arthur W. Meyer</i>	47
REFERENCES	69
PLATES III-IX, AND EXPLANATION OF PLATES.....	<i>following</i> 70
III. SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BLOOD OF THE GUINEA PIG IN EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY, by <i>Lewis M. McCormick</i>	73
REFERENCES	106
PLATE I AND EXPLANATION OF PLATE.....	<i>following</i> 108

PART I. THE SYMPTOMATOLOGY AND GROSS
MORPHOLOGY OF EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY
IN THE GUINEA PIG

I. THE SYMPTOMATOLOGY¹ AND GROSS MORPHOLOGY OF EXPERIMENTAL SCURVY IN THE GUINEA PIG²

By ARTHUR W. MEYER

CONDITIONS OF THE EXPERIMENT

A so-called synthetic, basic diet was not used in these experiments, partly because my original object was to ascertain, if possible, the causes for the appearance of peculiar phenomena in guinea pigs kept on ordinary feeds and used in experimental anatomy. Among these phenomena were marked nervous manifestations and permanent, as well as profound temporary, locomotor disabilities.

Competent investigators, both from at home and from abroad, who had seen some of these animals, were of the opinion that, if they suffered from experimental scurvy, the signs certainly were anomalous. A competent bacteriologist who saw some of them and inspected a number of the necropsies was of the opinion that death was due to bronchisepticus pneumonia. Upon my mentioning this to a prominent European endocrinologist, he stated that rabbits which he and a colleague had used years ago, and which had suffered similarly to my guinea pigs, were believed to have died from infection with an organism called "Bacillus cunnisepticus" by his colleague. However, some of my animals, which were lost after unavoidable exposure to cold, did not seem to me to have suffered from pneumonia. Moreover, the behavior of a few that survived longest fortunately reminded me of the pictures of Cowgill's '21 dogs, and this supplied the clue. Hence, I injected tomato juice subcutaneously after the method of Cowgill, and began the feeding of tender lettuce leaves to some of the younger animals. They recovered as marvelously as had Cowgill's dogs. I do not mean to imply, however, that Cowgill's dogs did not suffer from polyneuritis, or that some of the animals in our two large lots, lost after exposure, did not die of pneumonia.

¹ Since the occurrence of symptoms in an animal always is a matter of inference, I use this word in the title with some reluctance. It might seem preferable to use the word "signatology," but one hesitates to add another term—especially a hybrid—to the already grievous number. Yet there is no question that the common confusion of the words "symptoms" and "signs" often leaves an author's meaning obscure. This is true also in the literature on scurvy. Moriguand, Michel, and Bernheim '24, for example, state that they produced experimental scurvy in guinea pigs with all the symptoms of human scurvy, and Smith '27 reported that "two guinea-pigs showed none of the recognized symptoms of scurvy."

² I gratefully acknowledge generous support for this investigation from the Committee on Research of the American Medical Association.

I had not previously become suspicious regarding the dietary of our animals because we had used the same feed for almost a decade without difficulty, and during all that time every visitor had remarked upon the fine appearance and the large size of our experimental guinea pigs. But upon inquiry I found that the fresh lawn-clippings which formed a part of the feed had not been received regularly for some time.

Until vitamins are available in chemical purity, for experimental purposes, it will, to be sure, remain impossible to ascertain the exact dietary deficiency to which particular disabilities and lesions observed in experimental animals are due. And as long as the exact vitamin content of food, the need of a particular animal for vitamins, and the exact number of vitamins remain unknown, no one can be certain regarding his conclusions. To date, all our knowledge is largely empirical, and one might gladly wait upon the chemist were the subject not of such surpassing interest and outstanding importance, and did it not have such direct bearings upon all other experimental work. It was the latter fact that compelled me to turn aside from other investigations in order to determine, if possible, what cytological changes in our experimental animals had resulted from deficiencies in diet.

Ever since the possible rôle of vitamins has become known it has seemed to me that qualitative rather than quantitative deficiencies in diet might have been responsible for some of the changes reported in starvation. I have in mind especially changes similar to those reported by Meyer '17, although I have no evidence whatever supporting the view that the lesions of scurvy are due to ordinary inanition. It would be interesting to ascertain what cytological changes would result from a diet quantitatively sufficient, but lacking wholly in vitamins.

The guinea pigs used in these experiments were kept under controlled temperature, recorded three times a day, and were given a basic diet of raw alfalfa hay, rolled barley, and water, in abundance. In some series the alfalfa hay and barley were heated to 100° C. for an hour, with gas, with electricity, or with steam, separately and also together. Lawn-clippings, lettuce, orange juice, wheat germ, and evaporated milk were added singly, or in combination, to the diet of some of the series in order to determine experimentally the identity of the vitamin from the lack of which the animals had suffered.

The only noticeable effect of the presence of wheat germ or evaporated milk in the diet was a slight prolongation of the life of the pigs. Although 10 grams of one of these feeds, or of both, were fed daily, mixed with moistened rolled barley, it is not possible to say just how much of each ingredient the pigs ate. However, some animals which ate the mixture well survived no longer than those that ate very little. This would seem to indicate that the latter apparently received enough of other vitamins.

BEHAVIOR OF THE ANIMALS

The time at which the signs of illness appeared varied with the age of the pigs, although some fairly mature animals failed to succumb after several months on the raw basic diet. This agrees with the observations on human scurvy and with the splendid pioneering observations of Holst and Frölich '12. Jackson and Moore '16 also reported individual variations, although it is difficult to understand how they could produce scurvy with a diet containing green vegetables, unless the latter were given in exceedingly small quantities, or were of a kind of which the animals ate an inadequate amount. The native difference in resistance to scurvy, noticed also by Furst '12, suggested the possibility of developing a particularly resistant strain of pigs, which, in itself, might throw some light on the question under investigation. It is possible, however, that the differences in resistance noted are not due to hereditary differences in resistance to scurvy, but to differences in predilection for food on the part of the animals. If the bacterial flora of the intestine is a factor in this matter, the habits of the pigs also might play a rôle in these apparent native differences in resistance to scurvy.

Pregnant and fairly young animals, those weighing about 400 grams, suffered and succumbed earlier, although some difference in resistance was noticeable among all ages. However, Nabel '23 stated that pregnant animals die before they become scorbutic, and that even when the mothers are fed as long as 39 days on oat bran and milk boiled for two hours, the young show no evidences of scurvy. The non-pregnant in Nabel's series, on the other hand, all became scorbutic. Although I did not investigate this point especially, the few pregnant pigs among my series all suffered from scurvy both clinically and anatomically, and so did the young, and all succumbed from this disease.

The older animals usually were more resistant, and none of these became absolutely helpless in the posterior half of the body, as did the young animals, which suggests that such helplessness as that shown in Figure 1³ may not be due to a true paralysis. However, Smith '27 stated that in "chronic scurvy" the guinea pigs were "paralyzed" so completely that they could not stand, and lay in one position so long that decubitus developed. This paralysis was said to have extended from the pectoral girdle "down," yet Smith suggested that the lack of movement in these animals may have been due "to the great pain occasioned thereby." I never saw decubitus and none of my animals lived long enough after they became helpless to develop it. Helplessness always indicated death within a few days at most,

³ The figures for Parts I and II appear, consecutively numbered, on half-tone plates, those for each Part immediately following its text.

and I do not comprehend Smith's statement that great pain prevented *paralyzed* animals from walking.

According to Smith, "The first manifestations of vitamine deficiency in the guinea-pig are swollen and tender joints." I never saw swollen nor found tender joints in mature animals, and the first change noticed in the behavior of my animals was a lessened activity and a reduced interest in the feed and feedings. Poupart '99 mentioned weakness in man, and, according to Boerhaave '76, van Swieten stated that lassitude is one of the first symptoms of scurvy in men. Since our cages were only about two feet square, it is not easy to determine whether the animals felt lethargic first, but it seems a fair presumption that they did. Cohen and Mendel '18 also mentioned the presence of lethargy in their animals. There may also have been some anorexia, for the animals soon began to manifest little, and finally no, interest, not even in green feed exhibited before their cages. This reduced interest in the feed was noticed because the pigs first called less loudly and less insistently for it, and then gradually desisted altogether. The decrease in activity gradually increased until the animals sat still.

After several weeks on the basic diet, they showed some tendency to pick out the tender constituents of the hay and the smaller particles of the rolled barley, suggesting the presence of tender or painful teeth or difficulty in chewing, or both. Schepilewskaja and Jarussova '26 also stated that the pigs used by them ceased to shell out the oats after a time. Some of our animals were found apparently chewing most of the time during the later stages, and frequently were found to have a small morsel of chewed food in their mouths at the time of death. I did not, however, find that the pigs "were hungry and ate voraciously" till death, as reported by Smith of paralyzed animals in "chronic scurvy," and hemorrhagic, ulcerated, or gas-distended, foul stomachs would certainly make that unlikely. However, Poupart spoke of a canine hunger to the end, in man.

It is possible that the tendency to continued chewing movements in guinea pigs may be due to pain rather than hunger, for, as noticed also by Heymann '26, they do not seem to swallow. Since Poupart stated that the gums of children itched so intensely that they tore them into shreds with their finger nails, it is possible, but unlikely, that guinea pigs seek relief from a similar sensation by chewing. When the sensory effects of the presence of hemorrhage and edema in the periodontium are considered it will not be any more difficult to understand why the guinea pig chews incessantly than to account for a similar tendency on the part of a teething child.

All the animals, except some that died early, evinced some difficulty in chewing, and preferred soaked, or otherwise softened, food in this stage. Many of them, however, chewed at hard dry alfalfa stems even in late

stages, and pressure against or traction upon the incisors did not seem to cause pain. It is, of course, difficult to examine the molars, but I never discovered any sensitiveness, although it would seem that it must have been present.

The eyes of some animals lost their luster as the disease progressed, and a slight roughening of the hair, especially about the anterior portion of the body, was sometimes present in the later stages. This roughening became more general as a rule near exitus, although it often was slight or absent altogether. Only two animals among several hundred had glued lids for a few days, and in these neither the lids nor the eyeballs showed gross structural changes with a hand lens, although an excess of secretion was present.

In the later stages the animals seemed drowsy and closed the eyes more frequently and continuously. They also felt cool to the touch, and crawled under the surplus hay or any protecting material that was placed in the cages. Some of them were soiled with blood and urine about the anus and vulva, or with feces, or with all three, and in some a large soft mass of foul feces protruded from the anus for a week or ten days before death occurred. A few passed very soft or hemorrhagic feces or suffered from vesical incontinence during the later stages, probably due to hemorrhages into the musculature, the mucosa, or the cavity of the bladder. Since vesical hemorrhages were present in a pig that had lost only 8.4 per cent in weight, it is evident that they can occur in otherwise well-nourished animals. My observations confirm McCarrison's '21 in this regard, and I am certain that microscopic examination of the urine would reveal the presence of hematuria in a large percentage of cases.

The lower jaw and throat of some pigs were wet with a greenish fluid, and a foul odor was relatively common in the later stages of the disease; but diarrhoea or melena were infrequent. The condition of the stomach at autopsy, of gassed pigs, as well as the condition of the mouth and lungs, shows conclusively that the foul odor is largely gastric in origin. Even in cases in which gastric distension was moderate this odor was rather "unsupportable," as emphasized by Poupart in scurvy in man. It certainly is an odor characteristic of putrefaction, although Smith holds that there is no increased putrefaction. The presence of a small amount of foul discolored food thickly coated with mucus was common in the stomach.

Instead of sitting quietly in a corner, as most of the animals did, a few became very nervous and seemed apprehensive. They acted as if frightened and startled easily at attempts to take them up or upon the occurrence of a sudden noise. Some of these pigs stood upon their hind legs against the sides of the cage when alone or as soon as they were approached, and looked toward the solid ceiling as if they hoped to escape through it. That

these animals frequently assumed this attitude when alone was shown by the fact that the walls of the wooden cages were soiled and scratched at the level at which their heads and front feet touched them and by the packed condition of the sawdust and alfalfa. Some of these pigs executed what Kihn '22 called "Reitbahnbewegungen," if I understand the word correctly; anything that startled them caused them to run around the periphery of the rectangular cages, and that they often did so when not startled by any one was shown by the presence of a definite path in this region of the cages. The sawdust and feed were trampled down smoothly especially here, and somewhat also elsewhere, indicating that the animal had spent most of its time walking or running around. A few of the animals were so nervous that a sudden noise startled them so that they ran wildly around bumping their heads against the corners, until they fell exhausted and lay panting and helpless wherever they had dropped. These pigs ran around quite frantically, and one of them remained in a comatose condition and for an hour it could not maintain its equilibrium after it had been set upon its feet.

Aside from the statement of Hess and Fish '14, that the knee kicks of children may be increased in scurvy, I know of no observations such as those here reported, except the tremors in men mentioned by Boerhaave, the frightened look, the headaches, and the convulsions spoken of by Poupart, and the statement of Howe '20 and '21 that, in a dietary condition unidentified by him, the pigs were said to have been very nervous at one stage. Boerhaave also wrote of faintings and anxieties which often were suddenly fatal to men, of a contraction of the limbs, and of palsy and convulsions. He thought, however, that it was not a true palsy, because patients always recovered completely from it. Poupart also stated that the muscles in man may be rigid as boards, and Euglenus is said to have stated that the ham strings became contracted. Hart, Steenbock, and Smith '19 noted an "inability to use the hind legs which finally developed into an apparent paralysis of those parts," and Cohendy and Wollman '22 also spoke of a paralysis following the feeding of a sterilized diet. It is very interesting that the behavior of many of the guinea pigs in my series reminded me of the behavior of Hofmeister's '22 rats fed on polished rice alone. Indeed, Hofmeister's description could be adopted with but slight changes for the nervous animals in my series, and although rats apparently do not suffer from scurvy I cannot help but wonder if Hofmeister's rats suffered only from polyneuritis. The anatomical report of Kihn '22 seems fully to justify my doubt.

Cohen and Mendel '18 and Cohendy and Wollman '22 mentioned stiffening in the hind legs in guinea pigs on a scorbutic diet and the occurrence of an apparent or a pseudoparalysis. Morgen and Beger '15 and Bauman

and Howard '17 also observed difficulty in walking in rabbits fed on oats alone. This was noticed in most of my animals, except those that died early. It first becomes evident through stiffness and a tendency, confined to the posterior extremities, to change from a walk to a hop. Sometimes this tendency was not evident until shortly before death, although young animals frequently became absolutely helpless in the posterior extremities some days before they died. Figure 1 shows such an animal from McCormick's series. I saw the first of these helpless animals some years ago, and although they seemed hopelessly sick and were practically moribund, they were rescued as late as four to six hours before probable death by the feeding of tender lettuce, if they still would eat, or else by the subcutaneous injection of tomato juice. The pig shown in Figure 2 was rescued in this manner when it was completely helpless. It could not fully rise on its front feet even, but in sixteen hours after the subcutaneous injection of tomato juice it was standing up, though with difficulty and rather stiffly and imperfectly. It had lain helplessly on its side for twenty-four hours before, but recovered completely except for the permanent deformity and motor disabilities in its hind legs, shown in Figure 3. Dissection of the legs showed that the proximal tibial epiphyses had reunited in abnormal positions, and although ankylosis had been indicated clinically, gross and microscopic examination failed to reveal it. Yet these legs remained permanently stiff at the knee but pigs that walk stiffly may show no hemorrhage or swollen or grossly abnormal joints at autopsy.

The legs of this pig apparently were rotated outward below the epiphyseal region of the tibia during recovery from scurvy, thus producing the outward rotation seen in Figure 2. Both posterior extremities are not always affected or affected equally in this way, however. In several pigs only the right hind leg remained permanently outwardly rotated as shown in Figure 4. The apparent ankylosis at the knee was due to a spasticity and will be considered further with the microscopic examination. It was responsible for the posture shown in Figure 3 and these pigs made furrows in the sawdust with their hind feet as they tried to run, and frequently gathered so much alfalfa before them that they were halted. It does not seem improbable that the outward rotation of the legs on the thighs is produced mainly in the sitting posture of the animal and may be due not only to mechanical forces but also to lesions of the cord to be discussed later.

The hind feet of the normal guinea pig usually are rotated outward both while walking and while sitting, and when the proximal epiphysis of the tibia is detached from the diaphysis there is little hindrance to the tendency toward outward rotation which is normally present. Since ankyloses were absent in the knees of animals with permanently stiffened legs, the stiffness must have been due to other causes, and the rapidity with which these

helpless young animals regain their feet shows that detached epiphyses are not the sole cause of helplessness in the posterior extremities. This also is indicated by the fact that separation of radial and ulnar epiphyses does not prevent walking and that mature animals often show great difficulty in moving their hind legs.

Howe '20 and '21 attributed the abnormal position of the legs of the pigs in his dietary experiments on teeth to ankyloses, and suggested the presence of infection by adding that the condition was more like that in arthritis deformans and rheumatism "than many experimental conditions that have been called such." The rapidity with which these young animals regain their feet after treatment suggests very strongly that their ability to do so does not depend upon bony repair, although Wolbach and Howe '26 stated that new bone had been laid down twenty-four hours after the diet was changed. I regret that it is not clear to me just how this new bone can be so positively identified.

It is probable that the "mole or seal attitude" of the front legs of guinea pigs on a scorbutic diet spoken of by Heymann '26 is due to separation of the radial and ulnar and perhaps also of the humeral epiphyses, for I have observed it only in young (225-240-gram) pigs such as Heymann used. It is noteworthy that this investigator also stated that especially the hind legs become *limp* and seem to collapse. I never observed limpness except of the whole animal, but perhaps closer scrutiny would have revealed limpness in the hind legs before the presence of pseudoparalysis.

The only young, apparently paralyzed animals which did not survive indefinitely after treatment, or change in diet, and recovery from scurvy, were those in which the molar teeth had become tilted and fastened askew as shown in Figure 5. This abnormal position of the teeth made proper mastication difficult or impossible, and such animals invariably died of starvation, even if fed soft or green or chopped or steamed food. Sometimes they lived only a few weeks after recovery, and at other times several months. They always showed marked difficulty in chewing, and became greatly emaciated; but at necropsy I never found signs of scurvy.

A considerable number of animals objected to being taken up from the cages, as indicated by short, plaintive squeals; but firm palpation of the extremities or the trunk seldom caused any outcry suggestive of pain. It will be remembered that Chick and Hume '17 described a posture assumed by scorbutic animals which was regarded as characteristic by them. This they called the "faceache position." Delf and Tozer '18 also spoke of it, but only a very few animals in my large series assumed this posture even occasionally, and none of them held a "painful member twitching in the air." However, some of the pigs frequently reset their front feet without otherwise changing their sitting posture and others held one front leg up

as though it were painful to bear weight upon it. These legs always were outwardly normal, and no abnormality except slight hemorrhage was revealed in many such by careful dissection. Some of them contained not the slightest hemorrhage except in the axillae and none of the pigs responded by an outcry to very firm pressure upon the legs. Other pigs squealed when taken up, no matter how carefully, by clasping them about the trunk with one or with both hands. Since wholly unafraid animals which had not squealed before did this, it would seem that they suffered from pain. I never found that subcutaneous areas which were hemorrhagic at autopsy had been painful to pressure before death and since no gross lesion was present in the extremities which the animals favored, I am inclined to think that any pain they may have suffered was due to involvement of the nervous system, such as was found upon microscopic examination. Among the significant older observations on this matter are those of Champlain quoted by Hektoen '26 to the effect that patients afflicted with scurvy suffered "severe pain in the arms and legs causing great distress; and because of the contraction of the nerves, the patients could not walk. Even passive movements were painful."

Except in the case of two newborn and a few young pigs none of my animals had swollen joints. As stated by Robb, Medes, McClendon, Graham, and Murphy '21, it is not improbable that the presence or absence of infection or hemorrhage may be a determining factor in this matter, for whenever, as Howe '21 found in his dietary experiments, a condition of the jaws which simulated pyorrhea alveolaris developed, it would not be surprising if arthritis occurred with its accompaniment of swelling and pain. Intensely hemorrhagic joints may show no noticeable swelling, but the latter accompanies epiphyseal separation in young animals.

Cohen and Mendel '18 reported the presence of a marked hypersensitiveness in guinea pigs which still ate well and gained in weight, but I did not find much indication of it. It would seem, however, that hemorrhage and edema in the periosteum and periodontia must cause pain, and Poupert recorded pain in the groin, leg, abdomen, and stomach as among the symptoms of scurvy in man.

None of the animals that were allowed to die or that were killed suffered from infected teeth or gums as in the dietary experiments of Howe. Only a few in other series had enlarged, but not necessarily infected, axillary nodes, and none suffered from abscesses. However, Moore and Jackson '16 found the axillary and inguinal nodes frequently enlarged. The only lesions accompanied by or suggestive of evidences of infection, in my series, were gastric and intestinal ulcers and a few cases of hydrothorax. It does not seem improbable to me that the latter may have resulted from causes responsible for the hemorrhages and edema, rather than from in-

fection. It is of interest in this connection that McCarrison encountered hydropericardium in polyneuritis in pigeons. The probable absence of infections was also indicated by the constant and gradual fall in body temperature confirmed by thermometric readings in his series by my associate, McCormick. The absence of fever was noted also by Moore and Jackson; but Smith spoke of the presence of "inflamed joints" at autopsy, although she also stated that "No infections occurred throughout the course of the experiments," and reported the presence of decubitus.

In most cases the approximate time of death could be predicted some days beforehand. The only exceptions were the relatively few cases of gaseous distension of the stomach, of hydrothorax, and one case of hemo-pericardium.

If adult animals were allowed to die of the disease they sat quietly in a corner, their heads drooping more and more with increasing weakness, until nose and mouth rested on the sawdust, some of which was found in the mouth after death. I am sure, however, that its presence was largely accidental. They usually fell over on the side several hours before death, the irregular breathing being accompanied by more or less spasmodic movements, which may be responsible for the statement of Heymann that guinea pigs die after repeated convulsions in chronic scurvy. Stimulation of the skin with a pointed instrument or wire intensified these spasmodic movements, which synchronized with the stimulation. Rapid repeated stimulation would bring on a more general spasm. The significance of these things upon the existence of paralysis is self-evident.

An interesting phenomenon in males killed with illuminating gas was the occasional regurgitation of semen into the bladder so that spermatozoa, pieces of hemorrhagic vesical mucosa, urinary salts, and coagulated secretion formed slightly firm, friable masses up to half a centimeter or more in size. Coagulation of the semen in the bent urethra apparently prevented complete ejaculation during the agonal contraction of the seminal vesicles and ductus deferentes. I have evidence suggesting that a similar regurgitation rarely occurs during life, and may be a factor in the relatively common occurrence of vesical calculi noted in our male guinea pigs. This, however, requires the examination of a larger series of animals for confirmation. At any rate the older urinary coagula never are as soft as pure coagulated secretion from the seminal vesicles nor as hard as the vaginal plugs, and they certainly seem albuminous.

CHANGES IN WEIGHT

All animals were weighed at approximately the same time of day, some daily, others twice a week, and still others weekly. Unaccountable daily fluctuations in weight were noted in all these groups and also in normal

animals. Hence, considerable precaution is necessary in using an individual weighing for the basis of a generalization. The initial weights were used in calculating the total loss of weight, although the initial were not always the greatest weights, for some pigs continued to gain for a while, as did some of Holst and Frölich's animals, after they had been placed on the scorbutic diet. Age is, of course, a very important factor in this matter.

Although I did not notice anything characteristic of scurvy in the loss in weight, it usually was very pronounced during the last week or ten days, as noted also by Holst and Frölich and by others. The former attributed it to a failure to eat and said that they would like to believe that it is due to the loosening of the teeth. But since the teeth always become loose very gradually, the sudden loss in weight scarcely can be due to a sudden change in the teeth and jaws, except that when the teeth become altogether too loose and other effects of the disease become more pronounced, the pigs finally cease eating altogether. Moreover, pigs die with relatively firmly set teeth, and that the failure to eat is not due solely to pain in the teeth is indicated by the fact that such animals will eat tender lettuce or grass or other tender greens when practically moribund, and will recover. Some young pigs will do so even after they have been completely helpless in the hind quarters for a day or more. As will appear later, the presence of decomposing food or gas or ulcers in the stomach, and other profound organic changes, no doubt seriously affect the desire of the animals for food. Although I have thought that painful or loose teeth, or both, may prevent an animal from eating, it would seem that great hunger, if present, would cause them to make more of an attempt to do so. Some animals too will eat tender lettuce leaves when first given them after a prolonged scorbutic diet, and then gradually desist and die.

It seems doubtful to me that the marked loss in weight toward the end can be regarded as characteristic of scurvy. As will appear later, one mature pig gained in weight although profoundly affected by scurvy. In older pigs the loss begins gradually and as soon as the animals are placed on the scorbutic dietary, and increases, with occasional slight remissions in some animals, to the time of the sudden drop which probably is the result of complete abstinence. Some of the pigs lost relatively little in weight, however, and most of them died with considerable subcutaneous as well as deep fat. In a few pigs the fat was intensely yellow, suggesting jaundice, but unfortunately no tests for bile were made on the fresh tissues in these cases, and microchemical tests on fixed tissues did not reveal any. Special trials have caused me to doubt the delicacy of these tests, however.

A very striking thing was the amazing loss in weight observed in a few animals upon the resumption of green feeding. This reached 10 per cent of the body weight in some cases for each of the first two days, and

probably is correlated with loss of fluid from the intestine and removal of it from elsewhere, and perhaps also with a utilization of fat made possible by the ingestion of vitamins.

Reference to Tables I, II, III, IV, and V will reveal the percentage loss in weight in the animals composing five of my series. Young growing animals very evidently suffered a far greater loss than is apparent, for their loss in weight was masked by growth, even if retarded, and a similar factor is concerned in pregnant animals, of which there were only a few. Since all pigs, except those withdrawn for special purposes, were killed while moribund, no large allowance need be made for losses in weight which might have occurred between the time of killing and that of probable natural death.

TABLE I, SERIES 1

No. of Pig	Sex	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Percentage of Gain or Loss	Duration in Days	Nature of Diet	Comment
1.....	F	852	649	20.3	53	Raw rolled barley, raw alfalfa hay, and water ad lib.	Died
2.....	F	644	327	49.2	107		Died
3.....	F	714	765	+ 7.1	131		Experiment stopped
4.....	F	920	507	44.8	107		Died
5.....	M	623	315	49.4	62		Gassed while dying
6.....	M	578	777	+34.4	136		Experiment stopped
7.....	M	543	320	41.0	51		Died
8.....	M	542	767	+41.5	136		Experiment stopped
Average initial weight of 5 that succumbed.....							716.4
Average initial weight of 3 that survived.....							611.3
Average loss in weight of former 5.....							42.0 per cent
Average loss in weight of latter 3.....							27.7 per cent
Duration of experiment for those that died.....							76 + days
Duration of experiment for those that survived.....							134 + days

The greatest loss in weight observed in any of the first four series was 49.4 per cent, which is not quite so large as that noted by Holst and Frölich, who used a different diet. This was sustained by a male pig with an initial weight of 623 grams (Table I), in a period of sixty-two days, while on a raw basic diet. The smallest loss on this diet was 20.3 per cent. The latter occurred in a full-grown pig. However, that the lack of maturity of the first pig was not the main reason for its great loss of weight is indicated by the fact that male No. 8, which weighed 81 grams

less, actually gained 41.5 per cent, although kept on the same diet for 136 days, or more than twice as long. Pig No. 6 followed a similar course. However, had these two animals been kept on this diet long enough, they no doubt would eventually have suffered a greater loss and succumbed in the end.

TABLE II, SERIES 2b

No. of Pig	Sex	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Percentage of Loss	Duration in Days	Nature of Diet	Comment
1	M	790	530	32.9	29		Died
2	M	970	650	32.9	42		Gassed
3	F	975	741	24.0	42	Heated	Gassed
4	M	910	622	31.6	34	rolled	Gassed
5*	M	827.5	830	+ 0.3	13	barley	Died of intra-pericardial hemorrhage
6	M	915	608	33.5	43	and	Died
7	M	858	656	23.5	31	heated	Died
8	M	1025	745	27.3	41		Died
9	F	820	645	21.3	56	alfalfa	Died
10	F	760	684	10	47		Died
11	M	1077	758	29.6	34	hay	Died
12	M	1000	689	31.1	54	and	Died
13	M	1037	737	28.9	49		Died
14	M	910	623	31.5	49	water	Died
15	M	985	713	27.6	58		Died
16	M	925	608	34.2	34	ad	Died
17	M	937	697	25.6	52	lib.	Died
18	M	815	567	30.4	34		Died
19	F	842	597	29.9	39		Died
20	F	915	600	34.4	31		Died
Average*	..	919.2	655.8	28.4	42.0		Died

* Number 5 was not included in the averages.

TABLE III, SERIES 3a

No. of Pig	Sex	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Percentage of Loss	Duration in Days	Nature of Diet	Comment
1	F	763	557	26.9	39		Gassed
4	F	722	522	27.7	32		Died
5	F	575	390	32.1	33		Gassed
8	F	722	507	29.7	36		Gassed
11	F	733	468	36.1	34		Gassed
18	F	593	430	27.5	32		Gassed
20	F	550	372	32.3	21		Gassed
Average.	..	665.4	463.7	30.3	32.4	Heated rolled barley and heated alfalfa and water ad lib.	

Since none of the females were pregnant, Series 3a strikingly illustrates the native differences in resistance in the same sex. This is illustrated by those that succumbed as well as by those that survived. Although it is possible that some of these pigs got alfalfa which was not as pure as that received by others, it is very unlikely indeed that this is responsible for the observed differences. It should not be forgotten, however, that the freshness of the alfalfa, and perhaps also of the barley, has much to do with the duration of survival of animals on this diet, at different times of the year.

TABLE IV, SERIES 4

No. of Pig	Sex	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Percentage of Loss	Duration in Days	Nature of Diet	Comment
15.....	F	400	270	32.5	40	Raw rolled barley, raw alfalfa hay, and water ad lib.	Gassed
16.....	F	540	375	30.5	44		Died
17.....	F	362	278	23.2	41		Gassed
18.....	F	455	330.5	27.3	43		Gassed
Averages..	..	439.25	315.9	28.3	42		
1.....	M	532	355	33.2	43	Gas-heated rolled barley, raw alfalfa hay, and water ad lib.	Gassed
2.....	F	530	385.5	27.2	43		Gassed
19.....	F	653	385	41.0	35		Gassed
20.....	F	514.5	365	29.0	32		Gassed
Averages..	..	557.3	372.6	32.6	38.25		
3.....	F	422	285	32.4	12	Electrically heated rolled barley, raw alfalfa hay, and water ad lib.	Gassed
4.....	M	515	345	33.0	33		Gassed
5.....	M	480	321	33.1	41		Died
6.....	M	457	353	22.7	30		Gassed
Averages..	..	468.5	326	30.3	29.0		
7.....	F	894	600	32.8	22	Electrically heated rolled barley and gas-heated alfalfa hay and water ad lib.	Gassed
8.....	F	762	560	26.5	22		Gassed
9.....	F	752	505	32.8	21		Died
10.....	F	727	559	23.1	21		Gassed
Averages..	..	783.75	556	28.8	21.5		

That the younger animals, as noticed also by Holst and Frölich, usually succumbed sooner is shown by the first group in Table IV. Although the average weight of these pigs was only 439.3 grams, their average loss in weight was only 28.3 per cent. The average duration was 42 days. On the other hand, the five animals in Table I, Series 1, with an average weight of 716.4 grams, lost 42 per cent and lived 76 days. Other animals in other groups lost but slightly, while some maintained their weight. However, if the alfalfa hay or the rolled barley, or both, was heated to 100° C. for an hour, by gas, electricity, or steam, the period of survival was

greatly shortened, even if the loss in weight at the time of death was less. Reference to Tables II, III, and IV will make this evident.

The third group of Series 4 (Table IV) had almost the same weight as Group I, but they lost somewhat more, although they lived only two-thirds as long as those in Group I. Group II of this series, which was 118 grams heavier, lost still more, although they lived only 71 per cent as long; but those in Group IV, which were almost twice as heavy at the start as those in Group I, lost but little more in weight and lived only a little more than half as long. They received heated barley and alfalfa.

TABLE V, SERIES 5

No. of Pig	Sex	Initial Weight	Final Weight	Percentage of Loss	Duration in Days	Nature of Diet	Comment
5.....	M	910	660	27.4	33	Raw alfalfa	Died
6.....	M	830	593	28.5	33	hay and	Died
7.....	M	1055	770	27.0	36	raw barley	Gassed
8.....	M	940	685	27.1	33	ad lib.	Gassed
Averages..	..	933.7	677	27.5	33.7		
9.....	M	1170	865	26.0	33	Raw alfalfa hay,	Gassed
10.....	M	732	517	29.3	35	raw barley,	Gassed
11.....	M	998	765	23.3	33	and wheat germ	Died
12.....	M	1055	790	25.1	36	ad lib.	Gassed
Averages..	..	988.7	734.2	25.9	34.2		
13.....	M	795	590	25.8	58 ^a	Raw alfalfa hay,	Gassed
14.....	M	873	910	+37	48 ^b	barley, wheat germ,	Died
15.....	M	740	560	24.3	45	and evaporated	Gassed
16.....	M	873	618	29.2	47	milk, ad lib.	Gassed
Averages..	..	820.2	669.5	26.4 (of 3)	49.5		
17.....	M	790	583	37.6	47 ^a	Raw alfalfa hay,	Gassed
18.....	M	1045	805	22.3	45	barley, and	Gassed
19.....	M	1140	820	28.5	41	evaporated milk,	Gassed
20.....	M	1051	752	28.4	42	ad lib.	Died
Averages..	..	1005.2	740	29.2	43.7		

^a These pigs would have died sooner but for a change in diet.

^b Death accidental.

The still older and heavier group of nineteen animals, comprising Series 2b (Table II), which averaged 919.2 grams, lost only a little more (0.1 per cent) in weight and lived no longer. That is, animals more than twice as heavy as the young pigs in Group I, Series 4, lived only a day longer, in spite of the fact that the average loss in weight was only 0.1 per cent larger. This splendidly illustrates the effect of differences in the degree of deprivation of vitamins.

The existence of marked individual variations in resistance toward deficiencies in vitamine C is evident also in this group of pigs. Since the exact ages of these animals were not known, although none were over two years old, it is possible, although not probable, that slight age differences may be a factor in the differences in resistance of the immature animals, but I only feel justified in concluding that immature, senile, and pregnant animals yield sooner.

Groups I and II of Series 5 (Table V), which were composed almost wholly of mature males ranging from 732 to 1,170 grams in weight, showed almost no differences in resistance. One of these two groups of four pigs each received the basic diet only, while the other received wheat germ in addition. All except one of these pigs were full grown at the time that they were placed upon the deficient diet, but their weight differed greatly, as indicated above. Their ages also differed by several months, yet the periods of survival of these eight pigs ranged only from 33 to 36 days and the loss of weight from 23.3 to 29.3 per cent. The first four, the weight of which ranged from 830 to 1,055 grams, had survival periods ranging from 33 to 36 days and a loss in weight from 27 to 28.5 per cent. It would perhaps be difficult to obtain other groups of animals with such variations in size and with so slight a difference in the times of death and total loss of weight, but nothing could better illustrate the old rule that like causes produce like results, and that the addition of vitamine B had little or no effect. This is probably due to the fact that the diet used was not deficient in this respect.

The weights of the pigs in the second group of this series varied from 732 to 1,170 grams; the periods of survival showed the same differences, but there was a somewhat larger difference—6 per cent—in loss of body weight. The striking uniformity in these results seems to imply rather uniform conditions as causes of death, and were it not for the fact that some of the animals in the other groups survived very much longer, I might have questioned my own earlier results. Since I know of no reason other than that of a difference in resistance, for the greater length of survival of some of the animals in the previous groups, I am encouraged to believe that such differences really exist. That this is probable is indicated by pigs in Groups III and IV of Series 5 which survived those in Groups I and II of this series and also some of those in Groups III and V which had exactly the same diet.

GROSS STRUCTURAL CHANGES

Full-term fetuses and young pigs only a few days old had the same gross lesions as older animals, except that the bony changes were more pronounced. This agrees with the observations of Ingier '15, although it

must not be overlooked that the duration of the scorbutic affection of the mothers is a crucial factor in the extent of the lesions.

No gross changes were encountered in the gonads, and marked, general subcutaneous edema or ascites was not encountered in this series. Among several hundred animals examined during the last few years, there was only one in which a decided anasarca was present. A slight amount of edema always accompanies hemorrhage, however, and some local edema is not uncommon in the internal organs and is especially common in the perivesical fat.

According to Smith "the parts first to evidence actual impairment in the intact animal are the joints and tendons." I took particular pains to examine carefully the articulations in a large series of mature animals at autopsy but never found them abnormal. Nor did I find the tendons affected, although I must add that I have not made an extensive microscopic study of them, and Smith supplies no evidence. The only lesion I saw near the larger articulations was hemorrhage into the periosteum in the immediate proximity of the articular cartilages, and while it is probable that extravasations into the articular cavities may occur from these regions, I never observed them in the knee, elbow, and other joint cavities.

Ulcers, or infections of the mouth grossly evident, *intra vitam* or *post mortem*, and gross evidences of hemorrhage into or from the gums themselves, and the presence of loose incisors never were encountered; but subcutaneous and deep hemorrhages were common and sometimes extensive and surprisingly symmetrical even as to detail. However, the occurrence of hemorrhages was very erratic. This appears also from the literature, as recorded in the experiments of Bauman and Howard '17, for example. Subperitoneal or retrobulbar hemorrhages in the orbit were not observed. The nature of the hemorrhages corresponded very well to that recorded in the literature on scurvy. Sometimes they were very slight indeed. Intracutaneous hemorrhages also occurred a few times. In these instances the appearance of the under surface of the skin of the abdomen and thorax suggested the presence of numerous small petechiae. They were rare, however, as reported also by Holst and Frölich, and Jackson and Moore.

Abels '24 stated that skin hemorrhages are present only where infection occurs, but microscopic evidences of infection were not present in these areas in my pigs. Neither was edema or rise in temperature present, and although no bacteriological examination was made of the hemorrhagic areas, no evidence of infection was noticed in the animals while alive or during the microscopic examination of the material. However, cultural methods were not used, and it is possible that the few animals affected by

hydrothorax suffered from pleuritic infection and that some may have died of pneumonia.

Almost all subcutaneous hemorrhages occurred on the ventral surface of the body. They were most common in the upper tibial, the anterior femoral, and the lateral, mid-thoracic regions; but I am unable to state as yet whether they tend to appear first in some particular region. Since the hemorrhages are, after all, erratic as to location, I surmise that they do not constantly occur first at any one place. The ventral hemorrhages seldom extended up the throat and over the mandible and down the whole abdomen, but dorsal hemorrhages also occurred. The distribution of the former corresponds in general with that in human scurvy as reported by Aschoff and Koch '19. They found the legs affected in 80 per cent of their cases, and it is on the anterior surface of the legs and on the thorax that I found hemorrhages most common in the guinea pig. I never found them in the feet, although they were present at the carpal and tarsal regions of young animals in which epiphyseal separation had occurred. They occur especially in places of pressure and movement such as the axilla, abdomen, and chest. This, to be sure, does not contradict the suggestion of Aschoff and Koch that gravity is a deciding factor in their production in man. The implications of the "capillary resistance test" of Hess '21 make both inferences probable. Were it not for the fact that guinea pigs sit still so much, and that the anterior tibial and femoral regions are not the most dependent parts, one might reach a similar conclusion regarding the effect of gravity as to most hemorrhages in the guinea pig.

Since the pigs ate barley out of cups, it is not improbable that pressure and friction from the edges of the cups upon the throat and lower jaw may have been factors in determining the presence of subcutaneous hemorrhages there, and it seems probable to me that obstruction to the blood flow from contact with the bedding, or with other parts of the body, as in case of the legs and head, may be responsible for the characteristic localization of most of the hemorrhages in the guinea pig.

The only dorsal hemorrhages observed were seen over the spines of the lower thoracic and upper lumbar vertebrae and in the dorsal scapular, brachial, femoral, carpal, and tarsal regions. Those over the lumbar spines were seldom more than 2 mm. or 3 mm. in size, but they occurred in a very large percentage of the animals. It does not seem unlikely to me that tension and movement at these points, and possibly also exposure with increasing loss of weight, may be factors in their production, and it is interesting that extensive ventral subcutaneous hemorrhages may be present in a mature pig that still is gaining in weight.

I never observed intra-articular hemorrhages. Muscle hemorrhages, on

the other hand, practically always accompanied subcutaneous hemorrhages, although the latter rarely were grossly absent; but I never found it to be true, as reported by Ingier '15, that there may be no lesions, but hemorrhages, in scurvy. The muscles most affected were those concerned in respiration, in locomotion, and in mastication, but I did not make a detailed, comprehensive examination regarding the particular muscles affected throughout the entire body of the animals. Extensor muscles, such as the triceps, also were involved. The subscapulares were frequently slightly hemorrhagic, especially near their origins, and sometimes they were extensively so. In a few cases the hemorrhage into the adductor muscles of the thighs and the flexors of the legs was in the form of striations as shown in the Roentgen-ray photograph, Figure 6. Hemorrhages into the intercostals at the costochondral regions were very common, and when restricted were confined to the fourth and fifth spaces. They usually involved the intercostal muscles, and very commonly were exceedingly intense and extensive. Subperiosteal hemorrhages were especially common here and over the processes of the mandible and the tibiae.

While describing changes at the costochondral junctions, Hess '21 wrote: "On closer examination a yellowish-white transverse line may be seen at the epiphyseal junction of the ribs." Since no epiphyses are found in the region of the distal extremities of the ribs, I presume that Hess was referring to the costochondral junctions. I surmise that the line referred to here is the "yellow bar" mentioned by Chick, Hume, and Skelton '18 as being surrounded by hemorrhage, and which they frequently found present at the costochondral junctions. It will be recalled that Fraenkel '04 also spoke of the presence of a reddish-yellow zone proximal to the epiphyseal line but not on the ribs. Although changes at the epiphyses of the ribs probably also occur, so far as I know no one has described any.

Even young guinea pigs, weighing only about 200 grams, may die of scurvy without the presence of very evident gross hemorrhages, or other gross lesions, except loose teeth, fatty livers, and thickening in the carpal or tarsal regions or at the costochondral junctions. There may be no gross hemorrhage in these regions, and there may be an entire absence of edema, and perhaps also of pain. As will appear later, the thickenings at the costochondral regions are due only to the reaction in the cartilages. This so-called beading of the ribs was particularly marked in prolonged cases in relatively young animals, i.e., in cases in which there was only a partial deprivation of the antiscorbutic vitamine. In young animals, in which the deprivation was complete, the interference with growth was so marked that the thickening of the costochondral junctions was wholly absent and in older animals the cartilaginous separation did not occur.

The condition in the carpal regions was quite different in cases in which epiphyseal separation had occurred at the distal extremities of the radius and ulna. In these cases considerable hemorrhage and some edema were present at the site of the lesion. If this separation is complete, trauma from pressure in sitting, and from movement in locomotion, also becomes a factor in the production of further hemorrhage, edema, and deformity. I do not imply, however, that hemorrhage or edema, or both, are never present before epiphyseal separation is complete. Both periosteal and subcutaneous hemorrhages are, in fact, frequently present before separation of the epiphyses has occurred in fairly young animals.

Bleeding gums were never observed. This agrees with the observations of Bauman and Howard. Holst and Frölich, too, found only one case in which the gums near the incisors bled easily, and noticed gingival ulcers near the molars but once. I never encountered them. In a few cases the gingival margins around the posterior molars were found bloody at necropsy, the blood very clearly having come up from around the teeth. This also was the conclusion of Holst and Frölich. It was hence an alveolar or periodontal, rather than an intragingival hemorrhage. However, Talbot and Petersen '13, who fed only oats, bread, and water to guinea pigs, found that the gums bled at the slightest touch. Likewise, Howe, who, however, did not pronounce upon the nature of the condition concerned in his experiments, stated that the gums were infected and bled copiously in some instances. Jackson and Moore '16 found petechial hemorrhages near the lower incisors in spite of the fact that they fed green vegetables and raw milk to produce scurvy, but Cohen and Mendel '18 did not encounter them. None of my animals showed evidences of hemorrhages into the gums or directly from them.

Slight intestinal hemorrhages were commonly present, especially in the walls of the duodenum and cecum. Hemorrhages into the stomach and gall-bladder were rare, but they were very common in the urinary bladder. They were especially common in the paravesical fat, and often were so intense that the bladder was imbedded in very dark edematous fat. I encountered only two cases of blood in the gall-bladder.

Hematuria, as determined by microscopic findings, apparently is common in scurvy in man, but Pestalozza '25 regarded the gross presence of blood in human urine so uncommon that he reported such a case in a boy ten months old, and pointed out that various investigators found blood in the urine upon microscopical examination in about one-fourth of all the cases of scurvy examined. Hematuria was present 10 days before death in one of my guinea pigs that had lost only 8.4 per cent in weight during 42 days.

Although the uterus sometimes seemed congested, gross hemorrhages were never encountered in it. Fresh blood seen on the vulva had a vesical or intestinal origin. It might also have been renal.

The incisor teeth of none of the animals were loose, and in some pigs all the teeth were still quite firmly set. In others only the last molars could be depressed with much force although they usually were loosened somewhat. It is possible that Holst and Frölich always found the molars loose because they used a different diet and differences in diet and age probably account for many contradictory observations.

However, in advanced cases the last molars almost always were loose and hemorrhagic at the root and could be depressed easily. They seemed somewhat looser in the mandible than in the maxillae. The loosening, and also the extent of absorption of the roots⁴ always was progressively less from back forward, a fact which may be related to the decreasing amount of use and pressure to which these teeth are subjected in chewing. Moreover, as the incisors become longer from disuse, in spite of retardation of their normal growth by the deficient diet, the molars would be protected from normal pressures and use in a progressively decreasing way from forward back.

If the rate of growth of the guinea pig incisors is at all comparable to that of those of rats, as revealed by Addison and Appleton '15, it is easy to see that this growth would not be a negligible factor in the course of four to six weeks or longer, in spite of the fact that lessened use would tend to affect the molars similarly as the incisors. It is possible that the incisors would become looser and that hemorrhages from the gums near them would occur more frequently, were the animals given food demanding greater use of these teeth than is required by the diet provided in these experiments. However, since the incisors are set so much more deeply into the jaws than the molars, they undoubtedly would not become loose so quickly.

If the very singular method of fixation of the molar teeth in the jaws of the guinea pig is considered in this connection, it is evident that hemorrhage into or edema of the periodontium alone could not detach them. Only absorptive changes capable of dissolving bone or cartilage can do so for the osteodentine and the "Knorpelzement" form a continuous osteoid, if not osseous, union in places.

The posterior molars were so loose in some cases that they offered practically no resistance whatever to extraction, and they could often be

⁴ Although guinea pigs have holodont teeth, I am using the word root because it is unequivocal and because of the lack of a convenient term for the implanted portion of such teeth. In the absence of another term constant circumlocution would be unavoidable.

depressed not only below the surface of the gums but below that of the alveolar processes, with the greatest ease. In many of the animals they were so loose and the roots were so greatly shortened by absorption that it was difficult to see why they were not depressed during chewing. However, no teeth ever had fallen out during life, as reported by Robb, Medes, McClendon, *et al.* '21. Although some animals died before the teeth became loose, one can use the looseness and degree of absorption of the roots of the teeth as fairly reliable indices of the stage of the scorbutic process.

The only reference to the absorption of the roots of teeth which I have found occurs in Poupart. He stated that the teeth of a scorbutic boy of ten years "*étaient rongées à la racine et ne tenient plus.*" Unfortunately the age of this patient raises the question of the normal absorption in the temporary teeth regarding which—and infection—Poupart is silent.

If a very loose molar tooth is extracted from a scorbutic guinea pig, a drop of gelatinous material usually is found adhering to what remains of the root, or occupies the place of it. After this semifluid material is wiped away, the free portion of the root is seen to have a thin irregular border, as shown in Figure 7. Although it is very evident that a considerable portion of the root, sometimes almost all of it, must have been absorbed, the portion that remained always seemed as hard as the rest, or as a normal root, except in the immediate neighborhood of the affected end. It is significant that molars that are still very firmly implanted indeed may show considerable shortening by absorption. They were not as strong merely because they had been thinned, by absorption.

No evidence was obtained indicating the presence of demineralization of the exposed portions, or crowns of the teeth, or of the implanted portions, as reported by Howe. Since Howe found the "tips of the teeth" to soften first, it is clear that this softening must have been due to external influences. This inference is strengthened by the fact that Morel and Mouriquand '21 found no change in the chemical composition of the bones of the guinea pigs in scurvy. Moreover, Howe found cavity formation, and according to him the teeth in the unknown condition reported by him, could be penetrated easily with a sharp instrument, and "large portions could be brushed away in the process of cleaning the jaws."

I never could establish that the teeth were more brittle, by attempts to break them, nor did I observe broken teeth more commonly in my series of scorbutic than in the stock animals. I never saw teeth chipped at the crown, nor broken off at the root, or elsewhere, although the loss of substance was not limited to the "cementum" as observed by Robb, Medes, and McClendon. Cohendy and Wollman '22 spoke only of a "loosening of the molars and osseous fragility characteristic of scurvy." Since the loss

of substance on the teeth occurs at and below the level of the gums, as indicated in Figure 8, it is clear that the roots can be fractured more easily and hence are more fragile, but this probably never occurs *intra vitam* because the necessary leverage could only be obtained upon the long incisors and the only fractures recorded concern their free portions. However, Smith stated that the teeth often were broken off, but she did not state whether the incisors only were so affected. Presumably this was the case. Since Smith's pigs were fed a diet which afforded little use for these teeth, and since some of the animals were kept as long as eight months on the special diet, the mere breaking of the incisors could hardly be taken as conclusive proof that they were more fragile. Guinea pigs will try to shorten overgrown incisors even when on a normal diet. Hence while not denying that the pigs used by Smith had more brittle teeth, the existence and genesis of this brittleness require further proof before it can be regarded as established in scurvy, for a change in brittleness implies a change in composition or structure or both.

None of the conditions described by Mellanby '20 in the teeth of puppies lacking vitamine A were encountered in my series of pigs. Tozer '21 also emphasized that it is the lack of A and not that of C which causes brittleness of the teeth. Tozer further stated that this phenomenon does not appear until much later than the evidences of scurvy, but it seems strange that Tozer should also have stated that the deprivation of A causes changes indistinguishable from scurvy.

Although Moore and Jackson stated that "In general the viscera possess no important gross change" in pigs fed pasteurized milk and timothy hay, gross changes were pronounced and constant in my series fed upon raw alfalfa hay, raw rolled barley, and dry milk powder.

Hemorrhages or ulcers of the oesophagus were not found in the small series of oesophagi examined for such lesions, but the stomach often was hemorrhagic and empty, except for gas and a small quantity of mucoid fluid. Sometimes it contained a small mass of foul-smelling, discolored alfalfa thickly coated with mucus, and occasionally it was enormously distended with gas alone. Apparently this distension came on during the last few days of life, and it usually led to rapid and unexpected death. Its exact cause remains unknown to me though the odor of the contained gas and that of the small amount of non-gaseous contents would seem to suggest putrefaction or fermentation, or both, as the source. Smith, however, stated that there is no increased putrefaction in scurvy in guinea pigs.

It was in these animals that the lower lip and throat were soiled with a greenish, foul-smelling fluid, some regurgitation apparently having accompanied distension. The contents of the stomach were found blood-

stained in only a few cases, and in these the source of the blood apparently was from the hemorrhages around the posterior molars, although small areas of congestion and hemorrhage into the musculature and gastric mucosa were not rare. This agrees with the findings of Holst and Frölich. Ulceration of the mucosa was common. Very often the latter contained small, dull-white patches, and in one case almost the entire mucosa seemed to be replaced by a thick, tough, whitish coagulum which was very adherent and apparently the result of necrosis. Pus was never grossly encountered.

Congestion of and hemorrhage into the walls of the duodenum were very common, but ulceration of it was not frequently observed, although I did not make a minute and comprehensive study of this matter. The small intestine usually was empty save for varying amounts of fluid and gas. The latter was large in amount and the former usually was so bile-colored that the entire small intestine looked bright yellow.

The cecum frequently was hemorrhagic, and usually was filled with gas, with semifluid, or with fluid material which sometimes was bile tinged but it was never impacted. Although the cecum frequently contained much fluid the pigs concerned did not suffer from diarrhea, and unless it accumulated very shortly before death its presence would seem to indicate a lowering of the absorptive power and also of motility.

Hess and Unger '17-'18 found no evidence of constipation, the ceca of their animals containing gas and semifluid substances. However, Cohen, Barnett, and Mendel '17-'18 suggested that the constipation following the feeding of milk "renders debatable the hypothesis that experimental scurvy of the guinea-pig is attributable to failure of normal intestinal movement." Although Cohen and Mendel '18 found the cecum full of fluid, or semifluid feces, they also found impaction common. It seems probable that the diet used was responsible for the impaction, for I obtained no evidence confirming the old idea suggested by Boerhaave and reiterated, on experimental grounds, by McCollom and Pitz '17, and also by Pitz '18, that scurvy is due to constipation. My observations upon the matter confirm the conclusion of Harden and Zilva '18.

The colon frequently was empty, but it often contained formed feces. In some animals the contents were soft, though usually very moderate in amount.

Not infrequently the entire alimentary canal was empty, save for a moderate amount of gas and a mass of soft feces which distended the distal extremity of the rectum and protruded from the anus. Such a mass of soft feces was present in some animals a week before they died and suggested that there must have been a great lowering of the rectal, if not of

the intestinal, tonus and probably also a reduction in peristalsis. This conclusion based upon the condition of the entire intestinal tract seems to be contradicted by the experiments of Smith, which revealed "no significant impairment of the gastro-intestinal tract of the guinea-pig in acute or chronic scurvy."

The rest of the alimentary canal of these animals was empty, as a rule, except for a moderate amount of gas. The intestines were never found distended markedly, and a striking thing at necropsy was the absence of peristalsis, which often is so active in a recently dead, normal animal. Severe pinching with the forceps of different portions of the intestine seldom evoked more than a purely local contraction in most of the animals, and exposure to the room temperature usually had no effect whatsoever in increasing it.

The spleen seemed slightly enlarged and darker in color and somewhat congested and firmer. However, since McCarrison found an atrophy of approximately 62 per cent, calculated per kilograms of original body weight, my impression apparently is incorrect, although I was unable to learn upon how many animals McCarrison's determinations were based.

The pancreas often seemed soft and fatty, and the liver, which never seemed enlarged, presented the most striking changes in color. It frequently was mottled or uniformly pale salmon yellow, but sometimes only the caudal margin looked yellow. The difference in color between a normal and a fatty liver is well shown in Figure 9. In other cases, especially the caudal portion of the quadrate lobe was as white as beef tallow, and the rest of the liver a pale pinkish yellow. That this whiteness was due to fat, both gross and microscopic examination clearly established. Just why the fatty change should be so marked at the caudal margins and especially in this portion of the quadrate lobe, I do not know. One hardly can assume the conditions for the removal of the fat from the blood are best here. The assumption of a fatty degeneration would seem to suit the facts better, although the cells most remote from the source of blood supply may suffer cytoplasmic damage first, and therefore present the evidences of fatty infiltration first.

In several instances the ventral surface of some of the lobes contained depressed, grayish-green patches, such as shown in Figure 10, and in one case the superficial venules stood out very clearly, as shown in Figure 11. Since the peculiar, apparently necrotic, depressed areas were seen in only three pigs, they may represent coincident rather than consequent lesions, although I had never seen them in normal animals. Bauman and Howard stated that "a large irregular, yellowish-white area, the size of a nickel" which was present on the anterior surface of the left lobe of the liver of

their pig, No. 2, was excised for examination, but I failed to find further comment regarding it.

Since La Mer and Campbell '20-'21 stated that their 40 scorbutic animals gave "no indication that the liver is affected by a lack of water soluble C" it follows that my pigs did not have scurvy or that they had scurvy and some other affection, or that La Mer and Campbell overlooked the fatty change.

The gall-bladders usually contained some bile, but several were empty and firmly contracted into small whitish bodies about 3×7 mm. in size. Since free bile apparently was present in the duodenum and small intestine of a number of animals, it is possible that hunger contractions such as observed by Boyden '26, or agonal contractions similar to those occurring in the seminal vesicles, were responsible for its empty condition, although a liver which has undergone an almost total fatty degeneration could hardly be expected to produce much bile. I am reminded, however, that Wells '20 stated that especially in alcoholics "it may be difficult to find, microscopically, any cell cytoplasm because of the fat, the tissue looking like fatty areolar tissue; and yet there may be no clinical evidence whatever that the liver function has been impaired by the process." Since the fatty change in scurvy and, I take it, also in alcoholic poisoning, never is uniformly distributed, I surmise that Wells' statement rests upon appearances found in the particular portion examined, for no one examines the entire organ microscopically.

I was unable to observe any correlation between the degree of fatty hepatic change and the extent of the subcutaneous hemorrhages. When the latter were pronounced the fatty transformation of the liver usually was marked, but the latter sometimes was very yellow when there were no hemorrhages. In some cases too the liver looked almost normal and yet the pig was dead of scurvy. The teeth likewise might be quite firmly set still and the liver have whitish, fatty areas on its caudal margin, and the kidneys also appear mottled. One pig in which this happened had lost only 18 per cent in weight up to death, and if the intense yellow color of the fat seen in some animals will be found to be due to bile, it is probable that a pronounced local fatty degeneration obstructed the outflow of bile in these animals.

The adrenals often were very pale pink or lighter yellow in color and partly congested, but I never found them grossly hemorrhagic. They usually were softer in consistency than normal, and in a few cases a small superficial area 2×3 mm., with a somewhat irregular raised surface, seemed completely degenerate, the capsule seemingly having undergone lysis. In most cases the adrenals appeared definitely larger, but in others

it was noted that they seemed normal or small even. La Mer and Campbell reported an increase in weight of 100 per cent and regarded this as a compensation hypertrophy. Bessessen '23, who made a special study of the weight of the various organs in the guinea pig in scurvy, found that the adrenals "undergo a tremendous increase in absolute, as well as relative, weight," averaging 78.8 per cent above the normal for corresponding body weight, with a loss of 16.3 per cent in body weight. He found an increase of 270.1 per cent above the normal in pigs dead of scurvy. This reminds one of the statement of Rowles '25 that the hypophysis increases 276 per cent (!) in scurvy, owing to congestion alone. Although Bessessen also stated that congestion may, at least in part, account for the increase in weight, he nevertheless added that his results "somewhat tend to confirm McCarrison's view that the changes during scurvy (and other dietary deficiencies) are explainable as due to general inanition." However, Hess '21 emphasized the fact that the conditions in starvation and scurvy are quite dissimilar.

Robb '21, *et al.*, also reported hypertrophy of the adrenal. If the word hypertrophy is used to imply merely an increase in size, this no doubt is correct, but if it is used in the stricter sense, then it is misleading to say that there is hypertrophy of the adrenals in scurvy. At least, none of the specimens examined from my series of animals showed either hypertrophy or hyperplasia, and that this was true also of McCarrison's specimens is indicated by the illustrations and the descriptive text accompanying them. Although McCarrison has been said to have reported hypertrophy of the adrenal in the guinea pig, he merely spoke of an increase in size, of the presence of congestion and hemorrhages, and of a doubling in weight. Although I cannot pass on the validity of his methods of chemical analysis, McCarrison further stated that the epinephrin content is nevertheless reduced by half and that degenerative changes were present in the cortex and medulla of the organ. These things surely do not imply the presence of an hypertrophy, unless by that is meant a mere increase in size.

The increase in size of the adrenals is due not only to congestion but to hemorrhage, and especially to fatty transformation. This will become evident in the discussion of the microscopic changes. Some of the adrenals apparently contained so much fat that a thick whitish fluid exuded upon section of them at necropsy. It is possible, however, that these adrenals were not normal before the experiment was begun.

The external appearance of the kidneys usually was normal, though they often seemed a little paler. Not infrequently they were yellowish-pink, so that the kidney, liver, and adrenal were indistinguishable in color, as shown in Figure 12. That this correspondence in color was not due to

anemia alone was established by microscopic examination. I never found them grossly hemorrhagic.

The lymph nodes showed little gross change except in the case of those that drained hemorrhagic areas. In a few cases not included in the series, the axillary nodes were definitely enlarged and apparently tender. Infection may have been present in these cases in spite of the evidences to the contrary, but they promptly returned to normal size upon the feeding of greens.

The lungs of many of the animals showed little or no change, but very commonly small areas were dark red and sometimes this was true of an entire lobe or lung even, suggesting the existence of a broncho- or lobar pneumonia. Microscopic examination, however, never confirmed this. Hydrothorax was present in only a few animals, and undoubtedly was responsible for some of the cases of unanticipated death. I am not able to suggest the real significance of these effusions, but am inclined to think that they may be due to the same factors responsible for the hemorrhage and occasional local edema.

The heart was grossly normal, except that it often seemed somewhat paler and flabby. One case of hemopericardium was encountered, but since the pig in which it occurred had been on a deficient diet only a very short time this case may represent a mere coincidence, although a careful examination of the fresh heart under the binocular in salt solution, disclosed no abnormality. It is possible that this hemorrhage had a similar cause as that in other regions of the body. I never saw a firmly contracted heart seen so commonly in normal guinea pigs, killed with illuminating gas, but some hypertrophy, such as reported by Hess '21 for man, may have been present. Since the guinea pig heart is so small I gave this matter no special attention, but the condition in the lungs and the presence of anemia make it very likely that some hypertrophy may have been present in both ventricles.

It always is easy to recognize a marked case of scurvy from the condition of the cleaned skull, or even from that of the mandible alone. Although the incisor teeth still fit quite snugly, in most of the cleaned skulls the molar teeth usually are so loose that they readily drop out. This is true especially of the last, or third group, but in marked cases all the molars and even the premolars are very loose. The latter are more likely to remain in position because of their greater curvature. This looseness is due to enlargement of the alveoli and decrease in size of the roots of the teeth due to gradual absorption. As already stated, the latter may be absorbed totally for a part of their length, and also become smaller in caliber by absorption on the circumference. The molars not only easily

drop out of the jaws, but they also drop into the alveoli in cleaned specimens, because of the shortening of their roots by absorption. The posterior molars may sink below the level of the alveolar processes. They never seemed more curved than normal and the loosening apparently did not interfere with normal occlusion. The presence of tenderness may have prevented wear from taking place in the customary way and at the usual rate, however, and under conditions of intermittent deficiency in the diet they may stand more obliquely and become worn abnormally.

The entire jaws, as well as the rest of the skeleton also suffered from absorption. Small portions of the alveolar processes were sometimes gone. I encountered partial absorption, but I never saw a case of complete absorption of the alveolar processes such as mentioned by Howe. It is clear, however, that this might occur if the deficiency lasted for a sufficiently long period of time. This absorption frequently produced defects in the outer walls of the mandibles opposite the posterior alveoli as reported by Holst and Frölich and as shown in Figure 8. When sufficiently marked it exposed the roots of the lower molars, but I never observed roughening which looked like erosion, on the mandible or on other parts of the skeleton as observed by them. This may be due to the fact that absorption was slower in my series, or that I did not clean a large series of entire skeletons and thus missed it. According to Howe, a condition like senile atrophy results from slow absorption, and a condition like caris from rapid absorption.

A similar condition of absorption was evident also on the lateral wall of the maxillae opposite the roots of the upper molars where the overlying bone is normally very thin.

That absorption occurs over the entire skeleton is indicated by the reduction in, or the absence of the customary relief, as well as by thinning. The latter is evident particularly on the coronoid and condyloid processes and on the coxal bones. All the large bones are smoother and look somewhat glassy. In young animals complete separation of the epiphyses occurs and the proximal portions of the shafts of the tibiae may be defective. If the duration of the deficient feeding is sufficiently long, or if the pigs are sufficiently young, spontaneous fractures might hence occur, but I never saw any. It is easy, however, to produce fractures and I surmise that epiphyseal separation has been mistaken for fracture in the living.

Cohen and Mendel '18 stated that in young animals the "joints," especially those of the wrist, may fracture spontaneously, but this location would seem to suggest epiphyseal separation on the radius and ulna, rather than fracture of the carpals. In older animals epiphyseal separation is especially common at the proximal end of the tibia. The late union of this epiphysis and the marked strain to which the proximal portion of the bone

is subjected in locomotion may partly account for this fact and the late persistence of a fibrous area in the diaphysis opposite the epiphyseal cartilage is mainly responsible for detachment of this epiphysis in relatively mature animals.

The detachment of the molar teeth and of the periosteum apparently is not due only to the hemorrhages, for they may be slight or absent in some areas. The same thing applies to separation of epiphyses. Since an actual decrease in caliber of the bones and of the roots of the teeth occurs, and since the latter also become shortened, it is evident that the process which is responsible for removal of bone is not merely a demineralization, a halisteresis. According to Pelkan '25 the deposition of calcium at the zone of temporary calcification is chemical and therefore not interfered with, while resorption is cellular and therefore interfered with, thus causing a broadening of the calcified zone. Although I do not fully comprehend this explanation, all the evidence I have obtained so far indicates that a chemical and not a directly cellular activity is responsible for the absorption on bones and teeth.

X-ray examination of living or of dead animals, or of the partly cleaned skeleton, even in marked cases of scurvy in mature animals, did not reveal Fraenkel's line. The only line noticed is characteristic, but not of the deficiency, and is present in normal bones. It is shown in Figure 13. Talbot and Petersen '13 also failed to find Fraenkel's line during life, but stated that they nevertheless found X-ray evidence of scurvy in the bones after death. Except for the better exposure that can be obtained, it is difficult to see why this should be so. However, if the living animal could be placed in a good position, the shortening of the roots of the teeth by absorption should, to be sure, be revealed by the X-ray. The same thing applies to detached epiphyses, but Pelkan '25 stated that he could not, by this means, detect acute, or chronic scurvy in pigs weighing 250 grams. This may be due to the fact that the animals died before the effects were sufficiently pronounced, for Talbot and Petersen '13 found that pigs weighing less than 250 grams died in less than ten days, without "symptoms"⁵ of scurvy, after having been fed on oats, bread, and water. However, on another diet they well might live longer and show more extensive change.

Yang '24 published two skiagrams, one of a normal and a second of a scorbutic guinea pig, which he says show the characteristic changes in the bones. But since he does not say what particular changes are supposed to show, and since the photographs are very small, the thickenings at the costochondral junctions are not evident in the reduced figures. The pub-

⁵ One cannot but wonder whether these animals really died without symptoms, and signs no doubt were present.

lished skiagram of the scorbutic skeleton actually is lighter than the normal, but it is probable that rarefaction of the skeleton would be evident in skiagrams taken under proper safeguards if the scorbutic condition had been maintained long enough.

The periosteum usually can be stripped with the greatest ease. The entire mandible, for example, can frequently be shelled out as easily as though it were merely wrapped in a non-adherent covering. The membrane usually is loosest over the condyloid and coronoid processes and is separated from the bone by a small amount of hemorrhagic fluid or by blood. I am certain, however, that the hemorrhages do not cause the detachment. The gums and the soft parts over the entire hard palate can be detached with equal ease in many cases. That such conditions as these furnish abundant opportunity for infection is self-evident, yet I never encountered any in this series, or found evidences of them upon the bones themselves or in an elevation of temperature.

It is likely that the loosening of the periosteum is due to bone absorption, for the latter would necessarily release many perforating fibers of Sharpey, either wholly or partially. I never found the perichondrium detached or hemorrhagic, however, although degenerative changes occur in the costal cartilages. This probably finds its explanation in the differences in chemical composition of bone and cartilage.

Except for the fact that nerves commonly are included in hemorrhagic areas, and that changes in the nervous system were indicated by the behavior of many of the animals, I failed to find gross lesions in the nervous system. I inspected a fair number of spinal cords and brains, either in whole or in part, and also made some free-hand sections without encountering instances of gross hemorrhage into the meninges or nerve tissue itself. However, microscopic changes were present in both the central and the peripheral nervous systems and will be considered in the following section.

In some pigs the peritoneal surfaces of the transversus abdomines were puckered slightly in a most peculiar way so as to roughen the internal surface. I had never seen this before, do not know how to account for it, and do not mean to imply that this phenomenon necessarily is peculiar to scurvy. However, the profound degenerative changes present in the musculature in this disease suggest that it may well be associated with them, especially since the surface of the liver sometimes has a similar rough appearance.

It is very likely that the reports of different investigators of experimental scurvy in the guinea pig do not wholly agree regarding the behavior of the animals and the lesions, because of differences in the age of the animals and in the diets used. The basic diets used in these series un-

doubtedly contained some antiscorbutic, at least in the fresh raw alfalfa hay, even if not in the barley, and it is unlikely that all of vitamine C was destroyed by heating to 100° C. for an hour. This is indicated by the work of Barsikow '13, Daniels and McClurg '19, Davery '21, Vagliano '25, etc.

In my experiments the lesions were always the same, no matter whether the raw or heated basic diet was used alone or in supplemented form. They varied only in intensity, and this is what one should expect. However, if very young pigs are fed oats and water alone they apparently succumb before very pronounced gross lesions can occur, although it was by the feeding of oats that Holst and Frölich obtained the pioneering results. It is particularly interesting that they stated that pigs over 600-700 grams in weight are not suitable. I have not tried their diet, but with the diet which I used they were especially suitable.

Jackson and Moore stated that some diets produce more general scorbutic lesions than others, and Höjer and Westin '25 claimed that there is a distinct difference between the lesions produced in the teeth and the jaws by a complete and by a partial lack of C; but that was not my experience.

That my guinea pigs suffered from scurvy was established experimentally as well as anatomically. Those that received wheat germ in addition to the basic diet succumbed just the same, and none which were scorbutic could be saved by either yeast or wheat germ. That a lack of A in the basic diet was not the cause of the difficulty was established by the fact that the addition of dried whole milk neither prevented nor cured the disease. Jackson and Moore claimed that neither raw nor boiled milk prevented scurvy in their series, and Hess and Unger '17-'18 found that the addition of cod liver oil or abalone to a diet of oats, hay, and water did not prolong life. Mouriquand and Michel likewise found that the addition of butter, or of olive or cod liver oil to a diet of barley and hay (they do not state what kind of hay) did not prevent scurvy, and Findlay '21 found that autoclaved milk, caseinogen, cane sugar, and cod liver oil added to a basic diet of bran and oats did not modify the lesions of scurvy.

Hence it could not have been the lack of A which was responsible for the lesions produced, although I do not thereby imply that the lack of this vitamine does not produce osseous lesions such as described by Hume '21 and Tozer '21. I did not control the presence of an adequate amount of A in the diet by the method of vaginal smears, because of the infrequency of oestrus and because it seemed to me that animals which suffer such profound disturbances as those of scurvy might well experience irregular oestrus even in the presence of an adequate amount of A. However, the behavior of many of the pigs suggested that the oestrus cycle had not been wholly suppressed.

SUMMARY

So far as the gross lesions regarded as diagnostic of experimental scurvy in the guinea pig are concerned, I can add little except that the presence of fatty degeneration in the liver and absorption on the roots of the molar teeth, with the possibility of depressing the posterior or all of the molars, are constant morphologic signs. The extent of depression that is possible always is greatest in the last molars and decreases from back forward. Outwardly evident lesions in the bones and joints usually are absent in the mature guinea pig, and such animals may show evident signs of pain without the presence of swollen or tender joints and without hemorrhage in the extremities. They also may be very active and apparently unaffected and yet have extensive hemorrhages and have suffered considerable absorption on the roots of the molars and in the alveoli.

Some subcutaneous and muscular hemorrhage is almost always present somewhere at the time of autopsy, and duodenal, cecal, and vesical (urinary) and paravesical hemorrhages are common. The stomach, and in fact the entire intestinal canal, usually contains little food, and I have come to regard the lack of appetite and interest in food and also the lessened activity among the earliest signs of the existence of the scorbutic condition. An entire lack of interest in food always was an absolute indication of death within a few days no matter how well the animal seemed or how active it was. Increasing inactivity and weakness and increased loss in weight and appetite usually enabled one to forecast the approximate time of death except for the advent of sudden complications.

The new observations upon the gross pathology of experimental scurvy in guinea pigs here reported are:

1. The highly nervous condition of some of the animals.
2. The recovery of health of young pigs after a condition of complete helplessness in the posterior half of the body.
3. The occurrence of permanent locomotor disabilities.
4. Shortening of the roots of the teeth by absorption so that the molars can be depressed below the level of the gums.
5. The occurrence of pronounced gaseous distension of the stomach in some animals, and
6. Pseudopneumonic lesions in the lungs of others.
7. Fatty change, even to whiteness, especially of the liver, to a lesser degree of the adrenals, and microscopically also in other organs as will appear in Part II.
8. Necrotic areas in both liver and adrenals.
9. Degenerative changes in and fibrosis of the costal cartilages even in regions remote from the costochondral junctions.

REFERENCES FOR PART I

- ABELS, H., 1924. "Die Dysergie als pathogenetischer Faktor beim Skorbut," *Ergebnisse der inneren Medizin und Kinderheilkunde* (Berlin), 26: 733.
- ADDISON, WM. H. F., and APPLETON, J. L., JR., 1915. "The Structure and Growth of the Incisor Teeth of the Albino Rat," *Journal of Morphology* (Philadelphia), 26: 43.
- ADLOFF, P., 1904. "Ueber den Zahnwechsel von *Cavia cobaya*," *Anatomischer Anzeiger*, Band 35: s. 604-606.
- ASCHOFF, L., and KOCH, W., 1919. *Skorbut: Eine pathologisch-anatomische Studie*, 122 pages. G. Fischer, Jena.
- BARSIKOW, M., 1913. "Beiträge zur Frage des künstlichen Morbus Barlow bei Tieren," *Biochemische Zentralblatt*, 14.
- BAUMAN, L., and HOWARD, C. P., 1917. "Mineral Metabolism of Experimental Scurvy of the Guinea-Pig," *American Journal of Medical Science* (Philadelphia), 153: 650.
- BERKELEY, GEORGE, 1901. *Complete Works*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- BESSESSEN, DAN H., 1923. "Changes in Organ Weights of the Guinea-Pig during Experimental Scurvy," *American Journal of Physiology* (Baltimore), 63: 245.
- BOERHAAVE, 1776. *Aphorism van Swieten*, XI. Edinburgh.
- , 1745. *Praxis Medica*. De Scorbuto, T. V, pp. 101-117, cited from Berkeley.
- BOYDEN, E. A., 1926. "Behavior of the Human Gall Bladder during Fasting and in Response to Food," *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine*, 24.
- COHEN, BARNETT, and MENDEL, L. B., 1917-18. "Diet and Roughage in Relation to Experimental Scurvy in Guinea-Pigs," *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine* (New York), 15: 122.
- CHICK, H., and HUME, E. M., 1917. "The Distribution among Foodstuffs (Especially Those Suitable for the Rationing of Armies) of the Substances Required for Prevention of (a) Beri-beri and (b) Scurvy," *Journal of the Royal Army Medical Corps* (London), 27: 121.
- CHICK, H., HUME, E. M., and SKELTON, R. F., 1918. "The Antiscorbutic Value of Cow's Milk," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), 12: 131.
- COHEN, B., and MENDEL, L. B., 1918. "Experimental Scurvy of the Guinea-Pig in Relation to the Diet," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (Baltimore), 35: 425.
- COHENDY and WOLLMAN, E., 1922. "Quelques résultats acquis par la méthode des élevages aseptiques: I. Scorbut expérimental," *Comptes rendus, Académie des Sciences* (Paris), T. 174: 1082.
- COWGILL, GEO. R., 1921. "A Contribution to the Study of the Relation between Vitamin-B and the Nutrition of the Dog," *American Journal of Physiology* (Baltimore), 57: 420.

- DANIELS, AMY L., and McCLURG, NELLIE I., 1919. "Influence of High Temperatures and Dilute Alkalis on the Antineuritic Properties of Foods," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (Baltimore), **37**: 201.
- DAVERY, ALICE J., 1921. "Determination of the Minimum Doses of Some Fresh Citrus Fruit Juices Which Will Protect a Guinea-Pig from Scurvy, Together with Some Observations on the Preservation of Such Juices," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), **15**: 83.
- DELFT, E. M., and TOZER, F. M., 1918. "The Antiscorbutic Value of Cabbage. I. The Antiscorbutic and Growth-Promoting Properties of Raw and Heated Cabbage," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), **12**: 416.
- FINDLAY, G. M., 1921. "The Effects of an Unbalanced Diet in the Production of Guinea-Pig Scurvy," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), **15**: 355.
- FRAENKEL, E., 1904, 1906. "Untersuchungen über die Möller-Barlowsche Krankheit," *Fortschritte auf dem Gebiet der Röntgenstrahlen* (Hamburg), **7**: (1904) and **10**: (1906).
- FUNK, CASIMIR, 1916. "The Nature of the Disease Due to the Exclusive Diet of Oats in Guinea-Pigs and Rabbits," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (Baltimore), **25**: 409.
- FURST, J., 1912. "Weitere Beiträge zur Aetiologie des experimentellen Skorbutus des Meerschweinchens," *Zeitschrift für Hygiene und Infektionskrankheiten*, **72**: 121.
- HARDEN, A., and ZILVA, S. S., 1918. "Note on the Etiology of Scurvy in the Guinea-Pig," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), **12**: 259.
- HARRIS, KATHERINE D., and SMITH, ERMA, 1928. "A Histological Study of the Thyroid of the Guinea Pig in Experimental Scurvy," *American Journal of Physiology*, **84**.
- HART, STEENBOCK, and SMITH, 1919. "Studies in Experimental Scurvy. Effect of Heat on the Antiscorbutic Properties of Some Milk Products," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (Baltimore), **38**: 305.
- HEKTOEN, LUDWIG, 1926. "Early Postmortem Examinations of Europeans in America," *Journal of the American Medical Association*, **86**: 576.
- HESS, A. F., 1921. *Scurvy, Past and Present*. Lippincott, Philadelphia.
- HESS, A. F., and FISH, MILDRED, 1914. "Infantile Scurvy; the Blood, the Blood-Vessels, and the Diet," *American Journal of Diseases of Children* (Chicago), **8**: 385.
- HESS, A. F., and UNGER, F. J., 1917-18. "Experiments on the Scurvy of Guinea-Pigs," *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine* (New York), **15**: 82.
- HEYMANN, B., 1926. "Versuche an Meerschweinchen über die Beziehungen zwischen Skorbut und chronischer Tuberkulose," *Klinische Wochenschrift* (Berlin), **5**: 59.

- HOFMEISTER, FRANZ, 1921-22. "Studien über qualitative Unterernährung. I. Mitteilung. Die Ratten beri-beri," *Biochemische Zeitschrift*, Bd. 128 und 129: 477-486 and 540-556.
- , 1922. "Studien über qualitative Unterernährung. I. Mitteilung. Die Ratten beri-beri," *Klinische Wochenschrift* (Berlin), 1: 522.
- HÖJER, J., and WESTIN, G., 1925. "Jaws and Teeth in Scorbutic Guinea-Pigs. A Histo-pathological Study," *Dental Cosmos* (Philadelphia), 57: 1.
- HOLST, AXEL, and FRÖLICH, THEODOR, 1912. "Über experimentellen Skorbut. Ein Beitrag zur Lehre von dem Einfluss einer einseitigen Nahrung," *Zeitschrift für Hygiene und Infektionskrankheiten* (Leipzig), 72: 1.
- HOWE, PERCY R., 1920. *Food Accessory Factors in Relation to the Teeth and Bones*. Commonwealth of Massachusetts, Department of Public Health, Boston, 1: 228.
- , 1921. "Food Accessory Factors in Relation to Teeth," *Journal of Dental Research*, 3.
- HUME, E. M., 1921. "Comparison of the Growth-Promoting Properties for Guinea-Pigs of Certain Diets, Consisting of Natural-Food Stuffs," *Biochemical Journal* (Cambridge), 15: 30.
- INGIER, A., 1915. "A Study of Barlow's Disease Experimentally Produced in Fetal and New-Born Guinea-Pigs," *Journal of Experimental Medicine* (Lancaster, Pa.), 21: 525.
- JACKSON, F., and MOORE, J. J., 1916. "Studies on Experimental Scurvy in Guinea-Pigs," *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 19: 478.
- KIHN, B., 1922. "Ueber die pathologische Anatomie der sogenannte Polyneuritis bei Nahrung Insuffizienz," *Zeitschrift für die gesamte Neurologie und Psychiatrie*, 75: 241-278.
- LA MER, V. K., and CAMPBELL, H. L., 1920-21. "Changes in Organ Weight Produced by Diets Deficient in Antiscorbutic Vitamine," *Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Biology and Medicine* (New York), 18: 32.
- McCARRISON, R., 1921. *Studies in Deficiency Disease*, 268 pages. Froude & Hodder & Son, Oxford.
- McCOLLUM, E. V., and PITZ, W., 1917. "The 'Vitamine' Hypothesis and Deficiency Disease: A Study of Experimental Scurvy," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (Baltimore), 31: 229.
- MELLANBY, MAY, 1920. "Experimental Evidence Demonstrating the Influence of a Special Dietetic Factor on the Development of the Teeth and Jaws," *Dental Record*, 11.
- MEYER, A. W., 1917. "Some Morphological Effects of Prolonged Inanition," *Journal of Medical Research* (Boston), 36: 51.
- MOREL, A., et MOURIQUAND, G. (et al.), 1921. "Sur l'absence de troubles électifs du métabolisme du calcium osseux dans le scorbut expérimental," *Comptes rendus, Société de Biologie* (Paris), 85: 469.

- MOORE, J. J., and JACKSON, L., 1916. "Experimental Scurvy Produced in Guinea-Pigs by Milk and Milk Products," *Journal of the American Medical Association* (Chicago), **67**: 1931.
- MORGEN, A., and BEGER, C., 1915. "Ueber den schädlichen, auf eine Säurevergiftung zurückzuführenden Einfluss einer ausschliesslichen Haferfütterung," *Zeitschrift für physiologische Chemie* (Stuttgart), **94**: 324.
- MOURIQUAND, G., and MICHEL, P., 1922. "De l'action de certains aliments gras sur le métabolisme osseux adjuvants et antagonistes de la substance antiscorbutique," *Comptes rendus, Société de Biologie* (Paris), **86**: 1170.
- MOURIQUAND, G., and MICHEL, P., and BERNHEIM, 1924. "Les lésions du foie dans le scorbut," *Lyon Médical*, **134**: 626.
- NABEL, E., 1923. "Ueber die Beeinflussung des experimentellen Meerschweinchenskorbutus durch die Gravidität," *Zeitschrift für die gesamte experimentelle Medizin* (Berlin), **38**: 528.
- PELKAN, K. F., 1925. "The Roentgenogram in Early Scurvy," *American Journal of Diseases of Children* (Chicago), **30**: 174.
- PESTALOZZA, C., 1925. "Di un caso di morbo di Barlow con manifestazioni por friguenti," *Pediatria* (Napoli), **33**: 718.
- PI TZ, W., 1918. "Studies on Experimental Scurvy. II. The Influence of Grains, Other Than Oats, and Specific Carbohydrates on the Development of Scurvy," *Journal of Biological Chemistry* (New York), **33**: 471.
- POUPART, M., 1899. "Étranges effets du scorbut arrivés à Paris en mil six cent quatre-vingt-dix-neuf," *Histoire de l'académie royale des sciences*.
- ROBB, E. F., MEDES, GRACE, McCLENDON, J. F., GRAHAM, MAY, and MURPHY, J. J., 1921. "A Study of Scurvy and Its Bearing on the Preservation of the Teeth," *Journal of Dental Research* (Baltimore), **3**: 39.
- ROWLES, E. K., 1925. "Quantitative Study of the Hypophysis Cerebri of the Guinea-Pig in Experimental Scurvy," *Proceedings of the American Association of Anatomy, Anatomical Record*, **29**.
- SCHEPILEWSKAJA, N., and JARUSSOVA, N., 1926. "Zur Frage nach dem experimentellen Skorbut der Meerschweinchen," *Biochemische Zeitschrift* (Berlin), **167**: 245.
- SMITH, ERMA ANITA, 1927. "A Study of the Alimentary Tract in Experimental Scurvy (Guinea Pig)," *American Journal of Physiology*, **80**: 289.
- TALBOT, E. B., and PETERSEN, H. O., 1913. "Experimental Scorbutus and the Roentgen-Ray Diagnosis of Scorbutus. III. Experimental Scorbutus in Guinea-Pigs," *Boston Medical and Surgical Journal*, **169**: 233.
- TOZER, F. M., 1921. "The Effect on the Guinea-Pig of Deprivation of Vitamine A and of the Antiscorbutic Factor, with Special Reference to the Condition of the Costochondral Junctions of the Ribs," *Journal of Pathology and Bacteriology* (Cambridge), **24**: 306.

- VAGLIANO, M. S., 1925. "Persistance du pouvoir antiscorbutic du sirop d'orange," *Comptes rendus* [hebdomadaire], *Société de Biologie* (Paris), **93**: 602.
- WELLS, H. GIDEON, 1920. *Chemical Pathology*, 4th ed., 8°, 695 pages. W. B. Saunders Co., Philadelphia.
- WOLBACH, S. B., and HOWE, P. R., 1926. "Intercellular Substances in Experimental Scorbutus," *Archives of Pathology* (Chicago), **1**.
- YANG, FOO HAI, 1924. "Beiträge zum Meerschweinchen-Skorbut," *Zeitschrift für Hygiene und Infektionskrankheiten*, Band **102**, Heft 3/4.
- ZILVA, S. S., and WELLS, F. M., 1919. "Changes in the Teeth of the Guinea Pig, Produced by a Scorbutic Diet," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*, Ser. B., **90**: 505.

PLATE I, PART I

FIGURE	PAGE
1. Young pig completely helpless in the posterior half of the body. (McCormick series)	9
2. A similar pig after recovery, except for stiffness and outward rotation of hind legs. Taken during subsequent pregnancy.....	13
3. The same pig as in Figure 2, showing the permanently stiff, laterally rotated hind legs. Taken two years later.....	13
4. Another pig after recovery, with only the right leg permanently affected.....	13
5. Skull of a young pig after recovery from scurvy showing the molar and premolar teeth fastened in an incorrect position, causing starvation of the young animal	14
6. Peculiar striated muscle hemorrhages evident by X-ray in the extensor muscles of the thighs.....	25
7. Uncleaned right lower premolar and molars with partly absorbed roots.....	28
8. Lower premolars and molar showing absorption line beginning at the gums. Note also the small defects in the outer alveolar wall opposite the extremities of the roots of the second and third molars, on both mandibles. (The rest of the teeth were unfortunately not replaced before the photograph was taken)	29

PLATE II, PART I

FIGURE	PAGE
9. Photographs of fresh normal (<i>a</i>) and fatty (<i>b</i>) livers, to illustrate differences in color, the former retouched in areas of high lights.....	31
10. Degenerated areas on a scorbutic liver with roughened surface. The areas are outlined with ink.....	31
11. Distended superficial venules of the liver—present over the entire surface.....	31
12. Photograph of fresh kidney, adrenal, and liver to illustrate the fact that the first three may have the same color. The spleen was added for comparison	33
13. Irregular line in the proximal extremity of the tibia shown by X-rays, but unrelated to scurvy. Note also the unossified portion of the tibial diaphysis which shows as a gap in the anterior wall.....	36

